

ROBUST CATEGORIZATION OF POINT CLOUD DATA

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ABSTRACT

We present a low rank and sparse modeling framework and a computationally efficient algorithm for extracting Digital Terrain Models (*DTMs*) and foreground objects from Point Cloud Data (*PCD*). The model decomposes an input point cloud into three main components: bare-earth, spatially structured objects, and spatially unstructured objects or other spurious data, generating a richer output than standard bare-earth estimation algorithms. We test the proposed method using real Light Detection And Ranging (*LiDAR*) data.

Index Terms— Sparse models, low-rank models, bare earth, digital terrain models, point cloud data

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main building blocks of the *PCD* processing chain for geospatial applications is the *DTM*. The primary goal of the *DTM* (often referred to as bare-earth) is to extract all the data points that do not correspond to above-ground features in the scene. Accurate bare-earth extraction plays an important role in applications such as flood modeling, Line-of-Sight (*LOS*) analysis, and Above Ground Level (*AGL*) object height estimation.

Apart from the challenges associated with *PCD* such as noise, low and nonuniform sampling, medium characteristics, and the complex and highly diverse terrain types, there are generally no labeled data or explicit *a priori* information associated with the objects in the scene. Consequently, most currently existing models rely on heuristic arguments, spatial masking, and other hand-made rules to achieve an acceptable extraction of the bare-earth.

A plethora of algorithms have been developed over the past two decades to estimate the bare-earth from *PCD* (see for example [1] and references therein). Some of these algorithms work directly on the *3D* points while others work on a Digital Elevation Model (*DEM*). One of the most popular methods for bare-earth estimation is the progressive morphological filter introduced by Zhang et al. in [2]. It consists of applying elevation-difference thresholds and morphological opening operations iteratively, where at each iteration the size of the window (structuring element) is increased and the thresholds are recalculated. In [3], Elmqvist proposed a method based on active contours. The model minimizes an energy functional which is composed of rigidity and elastic terms. This method is limited to spatial neighbors (thus

only using local information), and the objective functional is composed of nonconvex terms. Evans and Hudak presented a multiscale curvature algorithm in [4] to process data collected over densely vegetated environments. In this approach, the *PCD* are interpolated at different grid-spacings and smoothed using a mean kernel. A pixel is classified as foreground if the value of the input data exceeds the value of the smoothed data plus a constant. A more recent approach was presented by Stevenson et al. in [5], where the *DTM* is estimated by iteratively applying a series of curvature-based segmentation and interpolation steps.

In this work, we propose an approach that provides two main advantages over current methods. First, our algorithm uses both local and global information to estimate the *DTM*. This is accomplished via spatially structured rank minimization. Second, in our methodology, we seek to provide a characterization of the foreground. We accomplish this by decomposing the foreground into spatially structured features, and spatially unstructured features.

Summarizing, we make the following main contributions:

- We present a new model for the categorization of *PCD* that employs rank minimization to exploit the redundancies in the bare-earth, and sparsity to model the non-ground features.
- We go a step beyond standard approaches by decomposing the foreground into spatially structured, and spatially unstructured components.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the proposed model for *PCD* and present an efficient numerical algorithm. In Section 3, we test the proposed model using a *LiDAR* dataset collected over Gulfport, Mississippi. Finally, we provide concluding remarks in Section 4.

2. MODELING *PCD*

Let the input point cloud be a set of points $X \subset \mathbb{R}^3$. Assume that a grid of size $n_i \times n_j$ has been imposed on X . Each grid cell is a function $f_{ij} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, that assigns to each grid cell the minimum height (z) value among all points within the cell. We have $f_{ij} = \min\{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n_{ij}}\}, \forall (i, j) \in \Omega$, Ω is the index set of entries $\{1, 2, \dots, n_i\} \times \{1, 2, \dots, n_j\}$, and n_{ij} is the number of points in the grid cell.

A minimum elevation *DEM* is generated from X and represented as

$$\mathbf{M} = \{\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j} | \mathbf{M}_{ij} = f_{ij}, (i, j) \in \Omega\}.$$

We make the following assumptions:

- The data, \mathbf{M} , can be modeled as a superposition of a bare-earth component and a nonground component.
- There is much redundancy in the bare-earth, i.e., it exhibits a high spatial correlation. As a result, the bare-earth component has low rank.
- Nonground features have sparse support.
- The foreground can be decomposed into a component having structured sparsity, and a component having unstructured sparsity.

Matrix decomposition techniques (see for example [6]) seek to decompose an input matrix into components whose physical meaning is given by a carefully chosen *prior*. For example, the Robust Principal Components Analysis (*RPCA*), model as introduced by Candès et al. in [7], decomposes an input matrix \mathbf{M} into the sum of a low-rank matrix \mathbf{B} and a sparse matrix \mathbf{O} by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{O}}{\text{minimize}} && \|\mathbf{B}\|_* + \tau \|\mathbf{O}\|_1 \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{O} = \mathbf{M}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{P1})$$

where $\|\cdot\|_*$ denotes the nuclear norm (the sum of the singular values), and $\|\cdot\|_1$ denotes the ℓ_1 -norm (the sum of the absolute values). $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j}$ is the low-rank component, $\mathbf{O} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j}$ is a foreground component which is assumed to be sparse, with support following the Bernoulli model, and $\tau > 0$ is a regularization parameter. The authors in [7] proved that under mild conditions, solving (P1) will recover the true low-rank and sparse components with overwhelming probability. The *RPCA* model has myriad applications including background subtraction in full-motion video, face recognition, voice and music separation, and text processing.

We apply (P1) to decompose \mathbf{M} into a bare-earth component \mathbf{B} , and a component \mathbf{O} that represents foreground objects. However, (P1) does not impose spatial consistency. Spatial consistency is important in this setting because nonground features are usually found in “clusters” and not as isolated pixels in \mathbf{M} . For example, consider a large structure such as a building. It is unlikely that a building will be represented as a single pixel in \mathbf{M} , but rather as a coherent block of pixels with similar values. Similarly, depending on the size and spatial extent of the scene, large structures will not necessarily be identified as foreground objects. If we consider a large building, it will be represented by a block of multiple rows and columns of approximately constant height. It is easy to see that such large structures may not be extracted from \mathbf{B} .

To address these two issues we propose modifying the optimization problem (P1) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{O} \geq 0, \mathbf{S} \geq 0}{\text{minimize}} && \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{B}) + \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{O}) + \tau_2 \|\mathbf{S}\|_1 \\ & \text{subject to} && \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{O} + \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{M}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{P2})$$

where $\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{B}) = \|\mathbf{B}\|_* + \mu_1 \|\mathbf{B}\|_{TV}$, $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{O}) = \tau_1 \|\mathbf{O}\|_1 + \mu_2 \|\mathbf{O}\|_{TV}$, and $\|\cdot\|_{TV}$ denotes the Total Variation (*TV*) seminorm. μ_1, μ_2, τ_1 , and τ_2 are regularization constants, and the operator \succeq denotes an element-wise inequality. The unstructured foreground is modeled by introducing a new variable, $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j}$, and minimizing its ℓ_1 -norm. The positive constraints on \mathbf{O} and \mathbf{S} enforce below-ground features such as holes and ditches to remain in the low-rank component.

Notice that we have introduced structural (spatial) coherence by adding a *TV* constraint to both the low-rank and foreground components. This has a twofold purpose. First, minimizing the rank will enforce global smoothness, but we would also like the low-rank component to be locally smooth, which is enforced by joint rank/*TV* minimization. Second, we model the structured foreground component by joint *TV*/ ℓ_1 -norm minimization to address our previous observation that nonground features are not necessarily isolated pixels in \mathbf{M} .

2.1. Optimization

The optimization problem (P2) can be solved using an Augmented Lagrangian formulation and alternating minimization (AM). The Augmented Lagrangian function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{B}) + \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{O}) + \tau_2 \|\mathbf{S}\|_1 - \langle \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{O} + \mathbf{S} - \mathbf{M} \rangle \\ & + \frac{\beta}{2} \|\mathbf{B} + \mathbf{O} + \mathbf{S} - \mathbf{M}\|_F^2, \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j}$ is a matrix of Lagrange multipliers, β is a positive constant enforcing the equality constraint, and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the matrix inner product defined as $\langle \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y} \rangle \triangleq \text{trace}(\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{Y})$. The AM scheme sequentially updates the variables $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{O} \rightarrow \mathbf{S} \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$ in each iteration. Each component is updated while the others are kept fixed. The subproblems involving \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{O} are solved via variable splitting and the Split-Bregman method [8]. The subproblem for \mathbf{S} is solved by soft thresholding.

The proposed method is implemented as described in Algorithms 1 and 2. In Algorithm 2, $\text{prox}_{\lambda h}$ denotes the proximal operator of the closed proper convex function h , defined as $\text{prox}_{\lambda h}(u) \triangleq \arg \min_x h(x) + \frac{1}{2\lambda} \|x - u\|_2^2$ (see [6] for details). In the proposed algorithm, the proximal operators that need to be computed admit closed form solutions in terms of a scalar thresholding, $\mathcal{S}_\lambda(u) = \text{sgn}(u) (|u| - \lambda)_+$ for the ℓ_1 -norm, and a singular value thresholding, $\mathcal{D}_\lambda(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{U} \mathcal{S}_\lambda(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \mathbf{V}^T$, for the nuclear norm (which is the ℓ_1 -norm of the vector of singular values). \mathcal{S}_λ acts element-wise on matrix-valued arguments, and $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U} \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T$ is the singular value decomposition of \mathbf{X} .

2.2. Discussion

By introducing spatial coherence terms in (P2) the proposed algorithm no longer enjoys the theoretical guarantees of (P1). As discussed in [7], *RPCA* assumes that the sparse component follows a Bernoulli model. However, this assumption does not necessarily hold in practice. For cases where the Bernoulli model is not appropriate, more complex models such as Markov random fields, and graph-structured sparsity

Algorithm 1 *PCD* decomposition algorithm

Input: $\mathbf{M}, \beta, \mu_1, \mu_2, \tau_1, \tau_2, \xi_1, \xi_2$ **Output:** $\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{O}, \mathbf{S}$ **Initialization:** Set $\mathbf{B}^0 = \mathbf{0}_{n_i \times n_j}$, $\mathbf{O}^0 = \mathbf{0}_{n_i \times n_j}$, $\mathbf{S}^0 = \mathbf{0}_{n_i \times n_j}$, $\mathbf{Y}^0 = \mathbf{0}_{n_i \times n_j}$ **for** $i = 0, 1, \dots$ **do**

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}^i = \mathbf{M} + \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{Y}^i - \mathbf{O}^i - \mathbf{S}^i$$

$$\mathbf{B}^{i+1} = \mathbf{F} \left(\mathbf{\Gamma}^i, \mathbf{B}^i, \|\cdot\|_*, \frac{\xi_1}{\beta}, \frac{\beta}{2\mu_1}, \frac{1}{\xi_1} \right) \triangleright \text{See Algorithm 2}$$

$$\mathbf{\Phi}^i = \mathbf{M} + \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{Y}^i - \mathbf{B}^{i+1} - \mathbf{S}^i$$

$$\mathbf{O}^{i+1} = \mathbf{F} \left(\mathbf{\Phi}^i, \mathbf{O}^i, \|\cdot\|_1, \frac{\xi_2}{\beta}, \frac{\beta}{2\mu_2}, \frac{\tau_1}{\xi_2} \right) \triangleright \text{See Algorithm 2}$$

$$\mathbf{O}^{i+1} = \max(\mathbf{O}^{i+1}, 0)$$

$$\mathbf{S}^{i+1} = \mathcal{S}_{\frac{\tau_2}{\beta}} \left(\mathbf{M} + \frac{1}{\beta} \mathbf{Y}^i - \mathbf{B}^{i+1} - \mathbf{O}^{i+1} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{S}^{i+1} = \max(\mathbf{S}^{i+1}, 0)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}^{i+1} = \mathbf{Y}^i - \beta (\mathbf{B}^{i+1} + \mathbf{O}^{i+1} + \mathbf{S}^{i+1} - \mathbf{M})$$

end for

have been proposed (see for example [9] and [10]). We use the *TV* seminorm to encourage spatial coherence. *TV* enforces gray-level (height) continuity, producing piecewise smooth solutions.

Another issue with the proposed algorithm arises when the scene being analyzed consists mostly of nonground features. In this case we should not expect the algorithm to succeed since there will be too few observations from the bare-earth. This, however, is expected and it is not seen as a limitation of our method.

3. RESULTS

We now present experimental results to test the proposed algorithm. The dataset used was collected over Gulfport, MS, with an Optech ALT-3001 linear mode *LiDAR* sensor at a resolution of 1m. The topography of the scene is mostly flat with nonground features that include vegetation, houses, and buildings. To run the algorithm on this dataset the point cloud was gridded at a grid-cell spacing of 1m and then interpolated to fill empty cells. When the collection geometry is such that the scene does not fit perfectly in a rectangular grid, pixels outside the valid domain are assigned the value of the closest valid pixel (within the same row whenever possible). Based on the selected grid-cell spacing the dimensions of \mathbf{M} are $(n_i, n_j) = (810, 708)$. We ran Algorithm 1 for 50 outer iterations with the following choice of parameters: $\beta = 20$, $\tau_1 = 0.055$, $\tau_2 = 2.4$, $\xi_1 = 0.17$, $\xi_2 = 1$, $\mu_1 = 0.1$, $\mu_2 = 0.7$. For each outer iteration we ran Algorithm 2 until convergence, or a maximum of 10 iterations. Algorithm 2 converges when $\|\mathbf{Z}^{k+1} - \mathbf{Z}^k\|_F < c$, where c is a small positive constant.

The decomposition of the Gulfport dataset into the 3 sought components is presented in Figure 1. The results obtained by the *RPCA* model are shown in Figures 1b and 1c. The results obtained by the proposed method are presented in Figures 1d-1f. In both cases the rank of the resulting bare-

earth estimate was 58 ($0.0819 \times \min\{n_i, n_j\}$). It is evident that *RPCA* can not distinguish structured outliers from unstructured ones, whereas in the proposed framework this is naturally handled. We believe that this could have an impact in certain tasks in automated scene analysis from *PCD*. For instance, we computed an overall accuracy of 96% in a building detection task on the Gulfport dataset using a thresholded \mathbf{O} as the detected buildings. The threshold was set at 2m, which is common for a building detection task. Figures 1g and 1h depict the clustering results obtained by *K*-means and the proposed method, respectively. Note how *K*-means is unable to obtain an accurate clustering result whereas the proposed algorithm achieves better performance while being completely data driven.

Algorithm 2 Inner loop of Algorithm 1

procedure $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Z}^0, h, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3)$ **for** $k = 0, 1, \dots$ **do**

$$\mathbf{\Psi} = \mathbf{X} + \lambda_1 \mathbf{Z}^k$$

$$\mathbf{T}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{T}} \|\mathbf{T}\|_{TV} + \lambda_2 \|\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{\Psi}(\mathbf{I} + \lambda_1 \mathbf{I})^{-1}\|_F^2$$

$$\mathbf{Z}^{k+1} = \text{prox}_{\lambda_3 h}(\mathbf{T}^*)$$

end for**return** \mathbf{Z}^k **end procedure**

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a model for the analysis of *PCD*, where we seek to decompose the input data into three components with different structure, namely a component which has low rank, a component with sparse support and spatial structure, and an unstructured sparse component. The model is optimized using convex optimization techniques, resulting in a simple and efficient algorithm. The efficacy of the method was demonstrated using *LiDAR* data. We also compared the results obtained by the proposed algorithm with those obtained by *K*-means clustering, achieving superior performance.

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] X. Meng, N. Currit, and K. Zhao, "Ground filtering algorithms for airborne lidar data: A review of critical issues," *Remote Sens.*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2010.
- [2] K. Zhang, S. Chen, D. Whitman, M. Shyu, J. Yan, and C. Zhang, "A progressive morphological filter for removing nonground measurements from airborne lidar data," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 41, no. 4, 2003.

Fig. 1. Decomposition of the Gulfport dataset by the *RPCA* model and the proposed method. (a) Original data (M), (b) *RPCA* bare-earth, (c) *RPCA* foreground, (d) proposed method, bare-earth, (e) structured foreground, and (f) unstructured foreground. Note that by using the *RPCA* model we are unable to separate the trees and vegetation from the houses and buildings. In the proposed method this distinction is modeled explicitly. (g) *K*-means clustering ($K = 3$) based on pixel intensity, and (h) the clustering result by the proposed method. Note how the data points are separated in terms of their geometric/structural characteristics while *K*-means is not able to obtain a meaningful result. (This is a color figure.)

- [3] M. Elmqvist, "Ground surface estimation from airborne laser scanner data using active shape models," in *Proceedings of ISPRS Commission III Symposium Photogrammetric Computer Vision*, 2002.
- [4] J. Evans and A. Hudak, "A multiscale curvature algorithm for classifying discrete return lidar in forested environments," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 45, no. 4, 2007.
- [5] T. Stevenson, L. Magruder, A. Neuenschwander, and B. Bradford, "Automated bare earth extraction technique for complex topography in light detection and ranging surveys," *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2013.
- [6] N. Parikh and S. Boyd, "Proximal algorithms," *Foundation Trends in Optimization*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2014.
- [7] E. Candès, X. Li, Y. Ma, and J. Wright, "Robust principal component analysis?," *Journal of the ACM*, vol. 58, no. 3, 2011.
- [8] T. Goldstein and S. Osher, "The split bregman method for l_1 -regularized problems," *SIAM Journal on Imaging Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2009.
- [9] Z. Zhou, A. Wagner, H. Mobahi, J. Wright, and Y. Ma, "Face recognition with contiguous occlusion using markov random fields," in *Proceedings of International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2009.
- [10] J. Mairal, R. Jenatton, G. Obozinski, and F. Bach, "Convex and network flow optimization for structured sparsity," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, nov 2011.